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Lysosomal storage diseases: possible use of nanophosphor-nanogold coated immunoconjugates in affinity purification of lysosomal transport vesicles

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Introduction: Lysosomal Storage Diseases (LSDs), a group of 40 or more metabolic diseases result from functional defects of lysosomal membrane transporter proteins. In a directed approach to characterization of molecular defects, we describe a protocol for affinity isolation of lysosomal transport vesicles as well as explore the potential of nanophosphor-nanogold particle based dual conjugates in isolation of membrane transporter proteins.

Methods: We have employed a proteomics-data based approach using consensus amino acid sequence motifs Tyrosine (GYXXfin) or Leucine-Isoleucine (D/EEXXXLI/L) targeting cytosolic domains in lysosomal membrane proteins for designing antibodies against custom synthesized peptides with signature or consensus sequence. Recombinant Constructs with DKFZp564K2464 (Human Transmembrane protein TMEM22 (accession UGID: 692851, a Gift from Dr. S. Wiemann), coding for a probable lysosomal transport protein were made and specific Yolk antibodies (IgYs) were then raised (1). Nanogold particles per procedure of Gupta and Tartakoff (1989) (2) and nanogold-IgY conjugates were then prepared.

Results & Discussions: Transfection experiments with HK 293 cells and cDNA reconstructs of fusion protein GFP-DKFZp564K2464 resulted in expression of a putative lysosomal transporter membrane protein with Mr 72000. In addition, we prepared a number of nanophosphors i.e., ZnS: Mn²⁺ ((Histidine capped)), CdS Cd-Se, LaPO₄:Ce/Tb, Eu:Y₂O₃, Y₂O₃:Tb and also BSA-Tagged ZnS: Mn (Histidine capped) nanophosphors and characterized with regard to their Photoluminescence, UV absorption spectra, XRD studies, SEM, TEM and AFM characteristics of nanophosphors make them suitable for preparation of Double Tagged Nanogold-immuno-Nanophosphors conjugates. as a useful reagent.

Various polymers and solid metal-based nanoparticles investigated for drug delivery, especially in cancer therapeutics, do not preclude their potential toxicity to patients. The affinity retrieval of membrane transport vesicles using a double nanotag (nanophosphor and nanogold particle) will be a novel way of studying cell biologic issues concerned with protein transport.

Conclusions: Functionalized multifunctional and multiplex nanoparticles are going to be the next generation of nanoparticles, for personalized and tailored cancer treatment.

Keywords: Nanophosphors-Nanold Immunoconjugates, Retrieval of Biomembranes

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